

PERCEIVED PROBLEMS IN USING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

The article considers one of the methods of teaching a foreign language - the communicative method. This work will be of interest to teachers of foreign languages who are innovative in their work. The author considers the possible problems that one has to face when working with this technique and presents various ways to solve them. Training is considered on the example of the well-known Headway course. In conclusion, the author comes to the conclusion that it is necessary to find a "golden mean" between teaching by the communicative method and the traditional one.

Foreign language has always been one of the main subjects in educational institutions. This is due to the various ties between Russia and other countries. peace. Mastering a foreign language contributes to the further development of new technologies, the creation of joint ventures, the exchange of specialists, expansion of the partnership. Which in turn affects the purpose of language learning - acquisition of oral and written speech skills. That is why the communicative approach is becoming more and more popular, that is, training should have a common communicative orientation, focus on the comprehensive development of the individual, capable and ready to use the language as means of communication at an intuitive level, formed on the basis of the conscious assimilation of the language theory, already translated into the plane of the unconscious. From which it follows that

the center of learning is the learner, and the system training involves the maximum consideration of the individual psychological, age and national characteristics of the personality of the student, as well as his interests. The object of training of this approach is speech activities such as listening, speaking, reading, writing, translation. So what is a communicative approach?

The communicative approach focuses language classes on learning communication, in terms of communication, the use of language for the purpose of exchanging thoughts. To do this, the focus of the lesson is on the creation and maintenance of students' need for communication and the assimilation in the process of communication of a professionally significant and representative of the general cultural the value of information. This approach

implements the basic requirements for modern educational process: communicative behavior of the teacher in the classroom; use of tasks that recreate situations of communication real life and involving the implementation of educational activities within the framework of such situations; parallel assimilation of the grammatical form and its function in speech; taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

Communication involves the use of the target language with the earliest stages of learning for natural communication purposes and functions or as close as possible to them, imitating them. That there is a communicative approach to language learning that focuses on learning to communicate, using language to exchange thoughts. To do this, they try to focus on the creation and maintaining the need for communication among students and the assimilation in the process of communication of professionally significant and representing the general cultural value of information. It's not always possible especially at the initial stage of education, since students do not yet have a sufficient level of proficiency in grammar and vocabulary of the language being studied and they have not yet developed a "sense of language". Alternatively, training can be built on a purely mechanical repetition of cliché phrases after the teacher for this or that situation, but it will be artificial, so called "pseudo-communicative" character, since when performing this action, the mental function of the student will be absent. At communication, in fact, we use speech means to convey the "personal" character inherent in each other.

During the lessons, students mostly communicate, but at the same time, writing and reading is also given time. Teachers try only to listen, they direct the activities of students, set exercises. When the students begin to actively discuss something, the teacher only observes. The question arises: should students be corrected when they do mistakes in colloquial speech, studying according to the communicative method? There is no exact answer, because some say that you need to pay attention only to elementary errors, some believe that it is not necessary generally intervene in the learning process, and someone believes that students need to be taught only accurate colloquial speech. The students themselves want so that teachers point out their mistakes to them, because many need take international exams, and for this fluent speech with classmates is not enough. Also, when teaching using this method, grammar is given little attention. Grammar rules are given haphazardly, often in the form of comments, as a result, the student does not understand the logic of English language, so can use it in a limited way. Consider a specific textbook - Academic skills, by Sarah Philpot and Leslie Kernick. This course is divided into teaching reading skills and writing, as well as teaching speaking and listening skills. Consider the first part is Reading and Writing. Each lesson contains several sections. The first is usually devoted to the development of reading skills, and reading is varied (scan reading, reading for gist, summary reading, etc.). Work on the text, as a rule, is preceded by classes in pairs, answers to questions. The second is aimed at developing the skills of "written language" (language for writing), this section is devoted to examples and

exercises for various writing situations: rephrasing, introductions and conclusions, language for presentations, etc. This is followed by a section on skills development writing is the writing of articles, essays and its components (paragraphs), summaries, reports, etc. The lesson usually ends with a section on working with the dictionary. A distinctive feature of the Headway - Academic Skills course is the study of the above skills at two levels: first in the context of the lesson, and then more fully at the end of each lesson (revision). In addition to the textbook, you can also use audio material with developed tasks, which contributes to a better perception of foreign speech, improves pronunciation and replenishes vocabulary.

In conclusion, I would like to note that the problems and questions that arise when introducing the communicative approach into practice are by no means

least does not belittle its merits in teaching foreign languages. As numerous studies on this issue prove, the communicative method is the most adequate means of teaching foreign language culture, since it develops a "sense of language" and corresponds to the tasks of teaching foreign languages in modern society - learn a language for the purpose of communication. The communicative approach quickly won people's trust. Many believe that grammar does not matter at all, which is important only spoken language. At first, all methods were directed mainly to study grammar. Now the communicative method has corrected this shortcoming, but they have ceased to study grammar. There is only one way out: you need to find a "golden mean" between the communicative teaching method and traditional.

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